

GOMOTOP CHIZIQLARNI KONSENTRIK HALQADA KONFIGURATSIYA MODULI.

Bobojonov Mahkam Davronovich

(UrDU Pedagogika fakulteti "BTM" kafedrası o'qituvchsi)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7906921>

Annotatsiya

Ushbu ishda tekislikda berilgan konsentrik halqa ichidagi 2 ta gomotop chiziqlar oilasini moduli orqali chiziqlar oilasining moduli topilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: gomotop, yopiq chiziq, egri chiziq, chiziqlar oilasi, funksiya, moduli

Quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz.

$$D_1 = \{x = (x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_2^2 < b^2, (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2\},$$

$$D_2 = \{x = (x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_2^2 \leq a^2, (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2\}, a < b.$$

$D = D_1 \setminus D_2$ soha konsentrik halqadan iborat bo'ladi.

Γ_1 – orqali D sohada yotuvchi, ichki va tashqi konsentrik aylanalarga gomotop bo'lgan barcha γ_1 yopiq chiziqlar oilasini belgilaymiz.

Γ_2 – orqali D sohada yotib uning chegaralarini tutashtiruvchi barcha γ_2 chiziqlar oilasini belgilaymiz.

Γ_1 – chiziqlar oilasining moduli

$$M(\Gamma_1) = \inf_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int \rho^2 dx = \inf_D \int \rho^2 dx = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \frac{b}{a}$$

ga teng.

Γ_1 chiziqlar oilasi uchun ekstremal funksiya quyidagi ko'rinishga ega [1. 30-33 bet].

$$\rho_{01}(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2\pi r} & (r, \varphi) \in D \\ 0 & (r, \varphi) \notin D \end{cases}$$

Γ_2 chiziqlar oilasining moduli

$$M(\Gamma_2) = \inf_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int \rho^2 dx = \inf_D \int \rho^2 dx = \frac{2\pi}{\ln \frac{b}{a}}$$

ga teng. Γ_2 chiziqlar oilasi uchun ekstremal funksiya quyidagi ko'rinishga ega [1. 33-35 bet].

$$\rho_{02}(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{r \ln \frac{b}{a}} & (r, \varphi) \in D \\ 0 & (r, \varphi) \notin D \end{cases}$$

R^2 fazoda Γ_1, Γ_2 chiziqlar oilasining chekli, tartiblangan to'plami $\Gamma = \{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2\}$ hamda tartiblangan $\alpha = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}$ musbat sonlar to'plami birgalikda berilgan bo'lsa konfiguratsiya berilgan deyiladi va $\alpha\Gamma$ yoki $\alpha\Gamma = \{\alpha_1\Gamma_1, \alpha_2\Gamma_2\}$ kabi belgilanadi.

$\alpha\Gamma$ konfiguratsiyaning moduli

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) = \inf \int_{R^2} \rho^2(x) dx$$

kabi aniqlanadi, bu yerda infimum barcha $\rho(x) \wedge \alpha\Gamma$ funksiyalar bo'yicha olinadi.

1. $\frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi} \geq \frac{\alpha_2}{\ln \frac{b}{a}}$ bo'lsin. U holda $\frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi r} \geq \frac{\alpha_2}{r \ln \frac{b}{a}}$ bo'ladi, bu yerda $a < r < b$.

Endi $\rho_0(r) = \max\left\{\frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi r}, \frac{\alpha_2}{r \ln \frac{b}{a}}\right\}$ funksiyani qaraylik. Yuqorida tanlab olishga ko'ra

$\rho_0 = \frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi r}$ bo'ladi va $\rho_0 \wedge \alpha_1\Gamma_1$ ekani ma'lum. $\gamma \in \Gamma_2$ lar uchun

$$\int_{\gamma} \rho_0(r) d\sigma \geq \int_{\gamma} \frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi r} d\sigma \geq \alpha_2$$

bo'ladi, chunki ρ_{02} funksiya $\alpha_2\Gamma_2$ uchun joiz. Demak $\rho_0(r)$ funksiya $\alpha\Gamma$ uchun joiz.

U holda

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) \leq 2\pi \int_a^b r \cdot \rho_0^2(r) dr = 2\pi \int_a^b r \cdot \frac{\alpha_1^2}{4\pi^2 r^2} dr = \frac{\alpha_1^2}{2\pi} \ln \frac{b}{a} = M(\alpha_1\Gamma_1) \quad (1)$$

ga ega bo'lamiz.

Boshqa tomondan $\alpha\Gamma$ ga joiz bo'lgan $\rho(x)$ lar to'plami $adm\alpha\Gamma$ $\alpha_1\Gamma_1$ ga joiz bo'lgan $adm\alpha_1\Gamma_1$ to'planning qism to'plami bo'ladi, ya'ni $adm\alpha\Gamma \subset adm\alpha_1\Gamma_1$. Shu sababli

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) \geq M(\alpha_1\Gamma_1) \quad (2)$$

(1) va (2) ga asosan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) = M(\alpha_1\Gamma_1) \quad (1^*)$$

$$2. \frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi} < \frac{\alpha_2}{\ln \frac{b}{a}} \text{ bo'lsin.}$$

U holda $\frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi r} < \frac{\alpha_2}{r \ln \frac{b}{a}}$ bo'ladi, bu yerda $a < r < b$.

Endi $\rho_0(r) = \max\left\{\frac{\alpha_1}{2\pi r}, \frac{\alpha_2}{r \ln \frac{b}{a}}\right\} = \frac{\alpha_2}{r \ln \frac{b}{a}}$ ga ega bo'lamiz.

Huddi yuqoridagi holdagi kabi $\rho_0(r)$ ni $\alpha\Gamma$ uchun joizligini ko'rsatish mumkin. U holda

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) \leq 2\pi \int_a^b r \cdot \rho_0^2(r) dr = 2\pi \int_a^b r \cdot \frac{\alpha_2^2}{\ln^2 \frac{b}{a} \cdot r^2} dr = 2\pi \cdot \frac{\alpha_2^2}{\ln \frac{b}{a}} = M(\alpha_2\Gamma_2) \quad (3)$$

Ikkinchi tomondan $adm\alpha\Gamma \subset adm\alpha_1\Gamma_1$ ekanligidan $M(\alpha\Gamma) \geq M(\alpha_2\Gamma_2)$ (4)

ga ega bo'lamiz.

(3) va (4) ga asosan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) = M(\alpha_2\Gamma_2) \quad (2^*)$$

(1*) va (2*) larni umumlashtirsak

$$M(\alpha\Gamma) = \max\{M(\alpha_1\Gamma_1), M(\alpha_2\Gamma_2)\}$$

ga ega bo'lamiz.

$$C' = \{x = (x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_2^2 = a\}$$

$$C'' = \{x = (x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_2^2 = b\}.$$

Adabiyotlar:

1. Дженкинс Дж. Однолистные функции и конформные отображения. М.: Изд-во иностр. лит., 1962.
2. Сычев А. В. Модули и пространственные квазиконформные отображения. Новосибирск: Наука, 1983.
3. Т. Azlarov, X. Mansurov. «Matematik analiz» I qism, Toshkent o'qituvchi 1984 y.

